

Reaction of diethyl mesoxalate with active methylene compounds : an interesting outcome

Sulakshana Karmakar and Manas Chakrabarty*

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, 93/1, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : chakmanas@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-33-23506790

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Abstract : Diethyl mesoxalate reacts separately with each of Meldrum's acid, indan-1,3-dione and diethyl malonate - all active methylene compounds - on neutral alumina either at room temperature or under microwave irradiation to furnish expeditiously the corresponding tertiary carbinols in very good yields. However, when the reaction of diethyl mesoxalate with a number of other active methylene compounds was tried similarly or by heating at 60-70 °C, the reactions either led to single products, which were too unstable to be isolated, or simply failed. Our findings, shedding new light on the reactivity of diethyl mesoxalate, are presented below.

Keywords : Diethyl mesoxalate, active methylene compounds, neutral alumina, *tert*-carbinols.

Introduction

It is well documented that indoles and indolyl Grignard reagents react with carbonyl compounds or their masked forms in presence of protic or Lewis acids or solid acidic catalysts, sometimes using alternative sources of energy, to form symmetrical bis(indolyl)alkanes (BIAs)¹, an important and well studied class of compounds having both natural as well as synthetic origins. BIAs are believed to be formed via the intermediacy of the corresponding indolyl carbinols. The latter have previously been reported to be generated by the reaction of indolyl Grignard reagents with pyridine-2- and 4-carboxaldehydes², by the solid-state photoreaction of the mixed crystals of nitrobenzaldehydes and indoles³, by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of indoles with (i) ethyl trifluoropyruvate using a chiral bisoxazoline-copper(II) Lewis acid as the catalyst⁴ and (ii) ethyl glyoxylate in basic, neutral or weakly acidic aqueous solutions⁵ as well as from the solvent-free reaction of indole with pyridine-4-carboxaldehyde using NBS as the catalyst⁶. However, the indolyl carbinols are usually not isolable from any acid-catalysed reaction carried out in solution, since they readily dehydrate in the acidic conditions to the corresponding alkylidene indoleninium cations, the azafulvenium salts. In most cases, the latter, though isolated in some cases⁷, are immediately attacked by a second molecule of indole as a nucleophile to produce symmetrical BIAs⁸. We had earlier demonstrated that the microwave-assisted, solvent-free reaction of indoles with diethyl mesoxalate, also

known as diethyl ketomalonate, on montmorillonite K10 clay⁹ (an acidic solid with large surface area) furnished expeditiously the corresponding indolyl carbinols as the major products together with the respective BIAs as the minor products¹⁰. This differential behaviour of diethyl mesoxalate, compared to other carbonyl compounds, was attributed to its structure, in which the carbonyl group is flanked between two electron-withdrawing ethoxycarbonyl groups.

We were, therefore, curious to check whether the reaction of diethyl mesoxalate with active methylene compounds would also lead to the formation of tertiary carbinols, particularly since the occurrence of Knoevenagel condensations¹¹ was a distinct alternative possibility in all the cases. Accordingly, the solvent-free reaction of a number of active methylene compounds with diethyl mesoxalate on neutral alumina¹² was studied. As a result, three different courses of the reactions were observed. Some of the substrates successfully reacted with diethyl mesoxalate to furnish, as expected, the corresponding *tert*-carbinols. The second category of compounds reacted to produce a single product (TLC) in each case. However, none of the products could be isolated since these molecules turned out to be very unstable. The rest of the substrates did not react at all with diethyl mesoxalate, even after prolonged heating or under microwave irradiation (MWI).

Results and discussion

To begin with, equimolar amounts of diethyl mesoxalate (**1**) and Meldrum's acid (**2a**) were adsorbed uniformly on neutral alumina (1 g for 1 mmol) at room temperature and subjected to MWI (400 W, 1 min pulse). The reaction was complete in just one minute, furnishing a single product. Its molecular formula was recorded as $C_{13}H_{18}O_9$ (HR FAB-MS), which corresponded to the sum of the molecular weights of diethyl mesoxalate (174) and Meldrum's acid (144). Pertinently, the LR EI-MS of this product did not record its actual molecular weight (318). The product exhibited a strong band at 3478 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum and signals at δ 4.27 (1H, br s) and at δ 78.4 (C) in its ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra, respectively. Considered together, these data strongly suggested that it was a tertiary alcohol. The rest of the data (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, LR and HR EI-MS and elemental analyses) were fully compatible with a *tert*-alcohol structure for the product. Thus, the product of the reaction was identified as the corresponding *tert*-carbinol (**3a**). The reaction is shown in Scheme 1.

scopically. These two reactions are also shown in Scheme 1, and the results observed for **2a-c** are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Reactions of diethyl mesoxalate with active methylene compounds*

Entry	Reactant (2)	Time, condition	Yield (%) of 3	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
1	Meldrum's acid	1 min, μw (400 W)	80	103–104
2	Indan-1,3-dione	15 min, rt	85	109–110
3	Diethyl malonate	10 min, μw (400 W)	65	oil

*Reaction with other active methylene compounds either led to single products which could not be isolated or did not react at all (see Text).

Surprisingly, our experience with other active methylene compounds was contrary to expectation. Thus, for each of dimedone, 4,4-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione, oxindole, ethyl cyanoacetate, malononitrile, cyanoacetamide and barbituric acid, the reaction with diethyl mesoxalate on neutral alumina at room temperature, at 60–70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or under MWI, as necessitated, took place

Scheme 1

Encouraged by this outcome, we decided to check the generality of this reaction using other active methylene compounds. Accordingly, each of indan-1,3-dione (**2b**) and diethyl malonate (**2c**) was separately treated with equimolar amount of **1** on neutral alumina. For **2b**, the reaction was complete at room temperature within 15 min, while for **2c**, MWI for 10 min was required for the completion of the reaction. In both the cases, the corresponding *tert*-carbinols **3b** and **3c** were isolated as the respective sole products, which were identified spectro-

successfully producing a single product (TLC) in each case. But in none of the cases, the corresponding product could be isolated in pure form even by applying milder reaction conditions, modified work-up procedures and milder isolation techniques. In each case, the product decomposed very fast. In a third set of experiments, both hydantoin and thiazolidin-2,4-dione did not react at all with diethyl mesoxalate even after prolonged reaction periods (several hours) at 60–70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or by applying higher power level (640 W) of MWI.

To summarise, for some of the active methylene compounds, the reaction furnished the corresponding *tert*-carbinols as the exclusive products in good yields. For some others, though the reaction proceeded smoothly to produce a single product in each case, the product could not be isolated in any of the cases. For the rest two active methylene compounds tried, the reaction simply failed. Though we are unable to explain the differential response of diethyl mesoxalate to different active methylene compounds, the present study unveiled a new and interesting property of diethyl mesoxalate, which constitutes the importance of the present piece of work.

Experimental

M.p.s were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR (Nujol) spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Impact 410 spectrophotometer, LR EI and FAB-MS (liquid matrix : *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol; +ve mode) in JEOL JMS-AX505HA, HR FAB-MS in JEOL JMS-700 MStation mass spectrometers and NMR (^1H : 500 MHz; ^{13}C : 125 MHz; both recorded in CDCl_3) spectra, including DEPT 135, in a Bruker DRX 500 NMR spectrometer. A BPL-SANYO Domestic Oven (800 Watt, 2450 MHz) was used at 50% power (400 Watt) for MWI. TLC was carried out on silica gel G (Merck, India) plates. Petrol ether refers to light petrol, boiling at 60–80 °C. Diethyl mesoxalate was purchased from Lancaster, and neutral alumina (active, standardised according to Brockman) was procured from Qualigens, India. All the reagents used were of analytical grade.

General procedure : A solution of **1** (1 mmol, from a stock solution of 0.76 mL, 5 mmol in CH_2Cl_2 , made up to 5 mL) was mixed with a solution of **2** (1 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (and a few drops of MeOH, when necessitated for dissolving the reactants) and adsorbed on neutral alumina (1 g). The solvent was allowed to evaporate off at room temperature, and the reactants-on-alumina were kept at room temperature or heated in an oven at 60–70 °C or subjected to MWI until the reaction was complete (TLC). The alumina was then allowed to cool down to room temperature, leached with 2% MeOH-EtOAc (3×20 mL), the solvent distilled off from the pooled extracts and the resulting pure product crystallised from EtOAc-petrol ether.

Spectroscopic data :

3a : Yield 254 mg (80%); m.p. 103–104 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_9$: C, 49.05; H, 5.66; Found : C, 49.12; H, 5.65; IR : 3478, 1776, 1757, 1737, 1301, 1209, 1142, 1082, 1049, 983, 883, 727 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR :

δ 4.86 (1H, s), 4.36 (2H, q, J 7.0 Hz), 4.35 (2H, q, J 7.0 Hz), 4.27 (1H, br s), 1.85 (3H, s), 1.78 (3H, s), 1.33 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 1.32 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : δ 168.2, 162.4, 106.0, 78.4 (all C), 53.0 (CH), 64.1 (CH_2), 28.6, 27.3, 14.2 (all CH_3); LR EI-MS : m/z 243 ($\text{M}-\text{HCO}_2\text{Et}-\text{H}^+$), 215, 170, 169, 143, 132, 115, 87, 69, 59 (100%); LR FAB-MS : m/z 341 ($\text{M}+\text{Na}^+$), 319 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$); HR FAB-MS : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_9\text{Na}$ ($\text{M}+\text{Na}^+$), 341.0848; Found 341.0859.

3b : Yield 272 mg (85%); m.p. 109–110 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$: C, 60.00; H, 5.00; Found : C, 60.08; H, 4.98; IR : 3439, 1765, 1739, 1719, 1308, 1265, 1238, 1149, 1067, 1046, 1003, 759 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR : δ 7.97 (2H, dd, J_1 5.5 Hz, J_2 3.0 Hz), 7.84 (2H, dd, J_1 5.5 Hz, J_2 3.0 Hz), 4.45 (2H, dq, J_1 11.0 Hz, J_2 7.0 Hz), 4.41 (2H, dq, J_1 11.0 Hz, J_2 7.0 Hz), 4.29 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 3.96 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz), 1.39 (6H, t, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : δ 195.8, 168.9, 143.0, 78.3 (all C), 136.2, 123.8, 57.9 (all CH), 63.8 (CH_2), 14.3 (CH_3); LR EI-MS : m/z 320 (M^+), 302, 247, 175, 174, 173 (100%), 147, 146, 105; LR FAB-MS : m/z 321 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$); HR FAB-MS : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7$ ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$), 321.0974; Found 321.0969.

3c : Yield 217 mg (65%); oil; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_9$: C, 50.30; H, 6.59; Found : C, 50.37; H, 6.57; IR : 3469, 1754, 1301, 1255, 1155, 1096, 1025, 861 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR : δ 4.51 (1H, s), 4.39 (1H, br s), 4.30 (4H, dq, J_1 4.5 Hz, J_2 7.0 Hz), 4.24 (4H, q, J 7.0 Hz), 1.30 (6H, t, J 7.0 Hz), 1.28 (6H, t, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : δ 168.5, 166.9, 79.1 (all C), 56.8 (CH), 63.5, 62.4 (all CH_2), 14.2 (CH_3); LR FAB-MS : m/z 357 ($\text{M}+\text{Na}^+$), 335 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$).

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